

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D4.15 Noise Management Toolset User Manual

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¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
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1 Introduction

In ANIMA WP4 an airport noise management tool chain has been developed, with which a variety of interventions for noise reduction can be simulated. This tool chain is described in detail in ANIMA deliverables D4.9 (Virtual Community Tool), D4.12 (Emissions Inventory model) and D4.14 (Noise Reduction Solutions Simulator).

Due to its complexity, this tool can only be used by aircraft noise experts. In order to extend the power of the tool to a wider audience, the most relevant parts of the tool chain have been implemented in an on-line tool. Two versions of this tool are available:

- Public Noise Toolset
This version has free public access and is mainly used to illustrate concepts related to airport noise management, as provided on the ANIMA Noise Platform. It only contains pre-defined use cases for educational purpose.
- Noise Management Toolset
This version is intended for professional users, providing them with an easy-to-use tool to assess different scenarios. It is available upon registration only.

ANIMA D4.11 provides a description of the tool chain as implemented as a web service, covering both versions.

The present document constitutes the User Manual for both versions of the tool. It should be noted that the toolset is continuously improved. In some cases this means that the layout of the user interface or the available functionalities as described here may not correspond exactly with the on-line tool. Therefore the user is invited to regularly check the user manual which can be downloaded from within the tool.

2 Background

2.1 Need for a toolset

The management of noise at airports requires making decisions concerning land-use planning, changes in air tracks, traffic distribution and others, considering their impact on noise exposure. For this purpose, extensive use is made of noise contours.

State-of-the-art tools generate information on noise exposure following a standard methodology defined in the Environmental Noise Directive (END) and Doc. 29 ECAC/CEAC – guidance on the calculation of aircraft noise exposure levels and the production of aircraft noise contours.

The noise contours calculated according to the END methodology are used to identify areas qualifying for insulation schemes, define land-use planning rules, noise protection zones and to communicate noise exposure data to the European Commission in a coordinated way.

The use of these noise models is complex and requires in-depth knowledge of aircraft noise and performance and air navigation. In addition, the user interface is usually rather complex, requiring significant training. Therefore, they are usually restricted to specialized users. Whereas at bigger airports such dedicated staff may exist, this will likely not be the case at smaller ones, which would thus have to rely on subcontractors to do this work, with the corresponding cost.

The ANIMA Toolsets have been developed to support airports with limited human and financial resources in their daily noise management tasks, without the need for highly skilled specialists.

As will be shown hereafter, the ANIMA Toolsets as applied to a specific airport, rely on a database that has previously been generated (off-line) by the aircraft noise specialists of ANOTEC with a dedicated tool (SONDEO) in a one-time exercise for that airport. Once this database is made available on the web, the authorized users will have access to the functionalities of the ANIMA Toolsets to perform their assessments in an easy manner.

2.2 Available versions

The noise toolsets are available in two versions for providing a complete set of functionalities to the general public with The Public Noise Toolset (**PNT**), as well as to other, specialized users with The Noise Management Toolset (**NMT**). Both versions are available on the web, implemented as a Software as a Service.

2.2.1 Public Noise Toolset (PNT)

The main objective of the Public Noise Toolset is to support, in an interactive manner, the explanations provided in the Noise Platform under the topic “Noise Mapping” (<https://anima-project.eu/noise-platform/noise-mapping>), on how

airport noise footprints are calculated following the methodology defined in the Environmental Noise Directive. It makes use of a virtual airport that allows the user to interact with the tool in order to visualize relevant inputs and outputs of a noise mapping tool. A set of traffic scenarios has been included, with variations derived from the base scenario (the reference scenario) to allow the user to understand different effects in noise contours. This version has free public access.

2.2.2 Noise Management Toolset (NMT)

This version is intended for professional users, providing them with an easy-to-use tool to assess different scenarios. It is available upon registration only. The NMT is designed to generate new scenarios in an easy manner, modify the flight operations, run processes, compare the results, and save changes.

2.3 Common features between the versions

2.3.1 Airport database

For each airport included in the tool, the following data is stored in the database:

Parameter	Description	Unit
Name	Airport name	-
IATA code	IATA code of the airport	-
ICAO code	ICAO code of the airport	-
Lat_ref	Latitude of airport reference point in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Lon_ref	Longitude of airport reference point in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Elev_ref	Elevation of airport reference point in WGS-84	M
T_av	Year average temperature	°C
Day period	Definition of day period (e.g. 06-18)	H
Evening period	Definition of evening period (e.g. 18-22)	H
Night period	Definition of night period (e.g. 22-06)	H

For each runway, the following information is stored:

Parameter	Description	Unit
Name	Official runway name (e.g. "03L")	-
Lat_rwy1	Latitude of runway end 1 in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Lon_rwy1	Longitude of runway end 1 in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Elev_rwy1	Elevation of runway end 1 in WGS-84	M
Lat_rwy2	Latitude of runway end 2 in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Lon_rwy2	Longitude of runway end 2 in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Elev_rwy2	Elevation of runway end 2 in WGS-84	M
Length_rwy	Runway length	M
Width_rwy	Runway width	M

Tracks are stored as a series of waypoints. These points may be derived from data in the relevant AIP, or may be determined by analysing actual flight tracks (radar/ADS-B):

Parameter	Description	Unit
Name	Track name (as per AIP or user defined)	-
Lat_P1, P2, P3, ..	Latitude of subsequent waypoints in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Lon_P1, P2, P3, ..	Longitude of subsequent waypoints in WGS-84	Decimal degree
Mode	Departure or Arrival	-
PoD_track	Period of day for which track is allowed (D/E/N)	-

2.3.2 [Single event database](#)

The single event database is at the core of the noise toolset. It contains all relevant combinations of:

- Aircraft type
- Type of operation: Arrival or Departure
- Vertical flight procedure („Profile“)
- Stage length (indicator for the weight at take-off)
- Runway
- Track

This database is generated with the SONDEO noise model by ANOTEC in an off-line process. For each airport to be included only the aircraft types that have to be considered in past, current and future calculations (current and future) need to be defined. All other data is already contained in the airport database or is available in the standard SONDEO database.

It is noted that the noise toolsets only allow calculations for those single events that have been included in the single event database.

2.3.3 [Scenarios](#)

A scenario is a dataset that represents a certain (noise) situation at an airport. It consists of a certain combination of the single events stored in the database.

To define a scenario the following is required:

- Number of operations of each single event
- Time of these operations (exact local time or period (Day, Evening, Night))

This information may come from e.g. the airport flight plan, radar data, etc.

In the PNT various pre-stored scenarios have been included, each highlighting a specific aspect of airport noise mapping. In the NMT the user may generate his own scenarios, for which various methods are available, as will be described in Chapter 4.

2.3.4 [User interface](#)

The user interface of both versions is the same. However, in the NMT more functionalities are enabled. In the following Chapters the user interface will be described by presenting different use cases.

3 Public Noise Toolset (PNT)

3.1 Objective

The main objective of the Public Noise Toolset is to support, in an interactive manner, the explanations provided in the Noise Platform under the topic “Noise Mapping” (<https://anima-project.eu/noise-platform/noise-mapping>), on how airport noise footprints are calculated following the methodology defined in the Environmental Noise Directive. It makes use of a virtual airport that allows the user to interact with the tool in order to visualize relevant inputs and outputs of a noise mapping tool. A set of traffic scenarios has been included, with variations derived from the base scenario (the reference scenario) to allow the user to understand different effects in noise contours. This version has free public access.

3.2 How to access the PNT

The Public Noise Toolset can be accessed through the button “Access to the ANIMA Noise Toolsets” on the Noise Platform (<https://anima-project.eu/noise-platform/anima-virtual-airport-scenario-showcases>), see Figure 1, by clicking on one of the indicated scenarios, or through the direct link <https://anima.anotec.es/home/map>.

Figure 1 – Access to the Noise Toolsets through the Noise Platform

3.3 User interface

When accessing the tool through the abovementioned button or the direct link, the virtual airport will appear (Figure 2). The toolbox on the left contains all features to work with the airport and its scenarios. It can be maximized or collapsed by clicking on the button.

The “Scenarios” tab in the toolbox gives access to the predefined scenarios (Figure 3). Each of these scenarios is also directly accessible by clicking on the corresponding scenario described in the Noise Platform.

Figure 2 – Initial screen when entering the PNT

Figure 3 – Elements of the user interface (example: scenario 21)

By clicking on the elements more information is provided (Figure 4). The legend found in the lower right corner including all dynamic elements presented over the satellite map are embedded thanks to *Google Maps, Imagery @2021 TerraMetrics*.

The standard Google Maps controls to change the background map or zoom in and out are also available.

Figure 4 – Detailed information on elements of the user interface (track, population, noise contour)

For each scenario the available noise contours are listed and the user may select those that need to be visualized (Figure 5). To view the flight operations of the selected scenario the corresponding button can be clicked (Figure 5). The flight operations window as presented in Figure 6 will appear.

Figure 5 – List of available and selected noise contours and access to Flight Operations info

Figure 6 – Flight Operations info window

Three main sections are present in the window:

- Actions
- Main statistics
- List of operations

By clicking on “Select an action..:” a list will appear with **actions** that the user can invoke. In the PNT only the “View statistics” option is enabled. The other options are only available in the NMT (see section 4). An enhanced view of the operations **statistics** corresponding to the current scenario is presented (Figure 7).

Figure 7 – The scenario operations statistics

This view provides detailed aggregated information on the distribution of the operations over the 3 time periods of the day (day, evening and night), and on the overall runway usage:

- Fleet composition per aircraft class, for each of the 3 periods of the day (day, evening and night)
 - o MR = Medium-Range aircraft (regional jets, A320, B737, etc)
 - o LR2 = Long-Range aircraft with 2 engines (A330, A350, B777, B787, etc)
 - o LR4 = Long-Range aircraft with 4 engines (A340, A380, B747, etc)
 - o TP = Turboprop aircraft (ATR, Dash-8, etc)
 - o Other = Other aircraft types, not being one of the above (general aviation, helicopters, etc)
- Route distribution: This graph gives the number of operations that follow each of the standard routes (tracks), for each of the 3 periods of the day.
- Operation-Runway: This graph provides information on how much each runway is used in the scenario, for each of the 3 time periods.
- Aircraft: Here the number of operations for each individual aircraft type is given. This constitutes the detailed fleet composition, also called fleet mix.

By moving the mouse over the various graphs, the actual values are displayed for the 3 time periods. The “Show active operations” button is used to filter out (from the list of operations) those records that have zero operations for all 3 periods of the day.

The **List of operations** presents detailed information for all the operations included in the current scenario. For noise mapping the number of operations during day, evening and night can be provided for each unique combination of the following parameters:

- Aircraft type
- Operation: Arrival (landing) or Departure (take-off)
- Profile: the flight procedure that the aircraft follows
- Stage: trip distance classification, an indication of the weight of the aircraft at take-off
- Runway: which runway the aircraft is using
- Track: which standard track (route) the aircraft follows for take-off or landing
- Subtrack: Used to simulate lateral dispersion (horizontal deviations from the standard Track)

By clicking on the header of any of the columns of the list, the list will be ordered according to the contents of that column.

The “Search” field can be used to filter the list of operations. Only those operations will be shown that contain (in any of its fields) the text in this box. In the following example the search text is “A319” (Figure 8).

Search <input type="text" value="A319"/>										
id	Aircraft	Operation	Profile	Stage	Runway	Track	Subtrack	Day	Evening	Night
47	A319-131	A	STANDARD	1	09	UDEN	0	0.78	0.22	0.09
48	A319-131	A	STANDARD	1	27	UDEN	0	4.42	1.23	0.49
49	A319-131	D	STANDARD	1	09	S&WDEN	0	0.78	0.22	0.09
50	A319-131	D	STANDARD	1	27	S&ED	0	4.42	1.23	0
51	A319-131	D	STANDARD	1	27	S&EEN	0	0	0	0.49

Figure 8 – Search option in the List of operations

The database of the PNT contains several comparisons between scenarios. These can be used to assess the difference between 2 scenarios, demonstrating the effect the change from scenario 1 to 2 has on the noise contours. These comparisons can be accessed through the Toolbox, in a similar manner as with scenarios (Figure 9).

Figure 9 – Comparison between different scenarios

4 Noise Management Toolset (NMT)

4.1 Objective

This version is intended for professional users (Authorities, Airports, Land use planners, Research Institutes, Universities, etc.), providing them with an easy-to-use tool to assess different scenarios. The NMT is designed to generate new scenarios in an easy manner, modify the flight operations, run processes, compare the results, and save changes. It is available upon registration only.

4.2 Registration

Registration is initiated by creating an account on the registration page, available at <https://anima.anotec.es/user/register> (Figure 10).

The screenshot shows the registration page for ANIMA Toolsets. The page has a header with 'ANIMA Toolsets' and navigation links for 'Public Map', 'Contact', and 'Account'. The main heading is 'Register', with links for 'Create an account', 'Privacy Policy', and 'Terms of Use'. The registration form includes:

- 'Complete Name' and 'Display Name' text input fields.
- 'Email address (E-mail)' text input field.
- 'Category' dropdown menu.
- 'Password' and 'Confirm password' text input fields, both showing a strength indicator of 'Strong Password'.
- A checkbox for 'I accept the Privacy Policy and Terms of Use'.
- A reCAPTCHA widget with the text 'I'm not a robot'.
- 'Cancel' and 'Create (under development)' buttons.

 The background features a large circular image of an airplane flying through a cloudy sky.

Figure 10 – Registration page

The registration system has a manual validation process to control the account requests and ensure the user authenticity. After gaining access to the NMT account, the user can login and see the dashboard as shown in Figure 11. The dashboard is designed to quickly access available data in the user space such as direct links to user map scenarios and comparisons.

Figure 11 – NMT dashboard

The account settings can be found in the upper left corner using the top menu. The user can update the registered information, change the password, or proceed with the account removal as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 – Account settings

4.3 Permissions

Permissions management is currently restricted to the system administrator at ANOTEC. The permissions features included in the dashboard will be enabled in a future version of the NMT.

4.4 Available airports

Each user will have access to the virtual airport, generated for the PNT, with the difference that in the NMT the user may change the scenarios, create new ones, etc.

Other airports may be added to the database through an off-line process, for which the airport “owner” should contact ANOTEC (see Chapter 6 how). Each additional airport is only visible and accessible to authorised users, assigned by the airport “owner”. All airports available to the user are listed in the corresponding section of the dashboard.

4.5 How to access the NMT

The Noise Management Toolset can be accessed through the button “Access to the ANIMA Noise Toolsets” on the Noise Platform (<https://anima-project.eu/noise-platform/noise-management-toolset>), although usually the access will be through the direct link <https://anima.anotec.es/user/dashboard>.

Clicking on the desired airport will give access to the NMT for that airport. The user interface is the same as for the PNT, described in Chapter 3, with the main difference that in the NMT advanced features are enabled, that allow for creating new scenarios.

4.6 Creating scenarios

The Noise Management Toolset allows the user to create new scenarios or edit existing ones. New scenarios are created as follows:

1. Clone an existing scenario
2. Provide scenario meta information
3. Change flight operations
4. Calculate noise contours
5. Save the scenario

All steps are available in the scenario layer of the toolbox (Figure 13).

Figure 13 – Scenario controls in the toolbox

4.6.1 Clone an existing scenario

A new scenario is created by pressing the “Clone” button:

An indication will appear that the request is being processed and once ready, the toolbox will be updated and the new (cloned) scenario will be available in the Scenarios layer of the Toolbox. The “Design” tag will be shown to indicate that this scenario is still not ready.

4.6.2 Provide scenario meta-information

The cloned scenario will have some default meta-information, which the user may adapt to his needs. To this end the “Edit” button of the new scenario should be pressed. A window as in Figure 14 will appear, in which the user may edit the name of the scenario and provide details that will be displayed in the toolbox.

The “Design” status is automatically enabled when a scenario has been recently cloned, but it can also be manually set for not showing yet on the map the results or related elements.

Figure 14 – Window to edit scenario meta-information

With the “Save” button of the window the information is stored in the database.

4.6.3 Change flight operations

The main objective for creating a new scenario is to assess the effect of a change in the flight operations. Access to the Flight operations window is the same as described for the PNT:

A window like the one shown in Figure 15 will pop up.

Figure 15 – Flight operations window of the NMT

Although very similar to the corresponding window of the PNT, in the NMT this window has two additional features:

- Download CVS (Operations)
- Upload CSV (Operations)

The first feature exports the current list of operations to a CSV file. This may be useful to use the data in another tool or for reporting. It may also be used to edit the current list of operations outside the NMT with a third party tool. The format of the CSV file is as shown in Figure 16.

```

NMT-sc21-flight-operations.ops.csv
* Aircraft,Operation,Profile,Stage,Runway,Track,Day,Evening,Night
737800,A,STANDARD,1,09,UDEN,3.77,1.05,0.42
737800,A,STANDARD,1,27,UDEN,21.37,5.94,2.37
737800SE,D,STANDARD,3,09,EDEN,1.26,0.35,0.42
737800,D,STANDARD,3,09,NDE,1.26,0.35,0
737800NV,D,STANDARD,3,09,S&WDEN,1.26,0.35,0
737800,D,STANDARD,3,27,NDEN,7.12,1.98,0
737800,D,STANDARD,3,27,S&ED,7.12,1.98,0
737800,D,STANDARD,3,27,WDEN,7.12,1.98,2.37
747400,A,STANDARD,1,09,UDEN,0.07,0.02,0.01
747400,A,STANDARD,1,27,UDEN,0.4,0.11,0.04
747400,D,STANDARD,8,09,NDE,0.07,0.02,0
747400,D,STANDARD,8,09,NN,0,0,0.01
747400,D,STANDARD,8,27,NDEN,0.4,0.11,0.04
7478,A,STANDARD,1,09,UDEN,0.12,0.03,0.01
7478,A,STANDARD,1,27,UDEN,0.66,0.18,0.07
7478,D,STANDARD,8,09,NDE,0.12,0.03,0
7478,D,STANDARD,8,09,NN,0,0,0.01
7478,D,STANDARD,8,27,NDEN,0.66,0.18,0.07
757PW,A,STANDARD,1,09,UDEN,0.3,0.08,0.03
  
```

Figure 16 – The flight operations CSV format

The second feature allows uploading a file with a new list of operations (may be the edited file described above, or a new one). The current flight operations will be replaced with the uploaded file. In the case that the uploaded single events contain a combination of aircraft, track, profile, operation, stage and runway, not available in the single event database this operation will be highlighted in red in the list, and will be ignored in the calculations.

Both features are very useful if in the new scenario many changes need to be made in the list of operations.

In the case that the changes to the cloned scenario are minor, manual edition of the flight operations is an option to consider.

The user may edit the number of operations for day, evening and night for each row of the operations list.

Several smart features are available through the “Actions” list, that facilitate common changes to flight operations (move, increase or reduce traffic)

Move traffic

This smart feature allows shifting a certain part of the traffic of a specific aircraft type or for all aircraft, from one track to another or from one time period to another.

Increase traffic

This smart feature allows increasing the number of operations of a specific aircraft type or for all aircraft, for a specific track and time period.

Reduce traffic

This smart feature allows reducing the number of operations of a specific aircraft type or for all aircraft, for a specific track and time period.

By pressing the "Apply" button, the updated list of operations will be created. Once all editions have been finalized, the new list of operations shall be saved by pressing the corresponding "Save" button at the end of the list.

4.6.4 Calculate noise contours

Once the required editions to the scenario have been done, the corresponding noise contours shall be calculated. To this end, the calculation procedure should be invoked by pressing the "Start" button:

The status tag of the scenario will change to "processing". Depending on the amount of operations, this may take more or less time. Once the calculations have been successfully finalised, the tag will indicate "Done". The user should then select the desired noise contours for visualization.

However, taking into account a range of uncertainties with problems that might occur on server side with unexpected user data, the response from the service might also be with an "Error" status. For such situations, the error is automatically reported and corrective actions are taken.

4.6.5 Save the scenario

Once the new scenario is considered satisfactory, the user should save it:

It is noted that the new scenario will only be available in the user space. Other users that have access to the same airport will not have access to this new scenario.

4.7 Comparing scenarios

If the user is selecting noise contours of the same metric from different scenarios, the “Save” button will produce a comparison view which can also be found in the comparisons list of the NMT account.

The comparisons meta-information (Name and details) can be modified if required.

5 Future work

The current version of the toolset is the result of a consultation process among relevant ANIMA partners. It is recognised that this version may not respond to all the needs of potential users. All users are therefore invited to contact with ANOTEC to request new or enhanced features, notify bugs, propose improvements, etc.

6 Contact

For any issue related to the toolsets you can contact ANOTEC through the following email address:

nmt@anotec.online

